

The CHIPS Database: A Repository for Reference Data on Chemical Analysis in Archaeometallurgy of Iron

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ABSTRACT

Archaeometallurgists interested in iron do not currently have access to extensive chemical reference data repositories. Yet chemical data is of crucial importance both for reconstructing ancient technical systems and socio-economic structures, by determining the operating conditions and the exchange networks. We are seeking to meet this need with the CHIPS database, developed on PostgreSQL. The goal is to provide the scientific community with global reference data in a standardised format. Chemical data can be selected using spatial, chronological or typological queries, thanks to the documentation of archaeological contexts and samples. Particular care has been taken to assess the quality of the chemical data, based on analytical metadata (types of analysis and technical characteristics of the analysers). In order to guarantee the interoperability of the database, the main tables are referenced by libraries, gazetteers and thesauri that are considered as standards by the archaeological community. The data can currently be consulted using a cartographic interface, and the development of a more advanced interface is envisaged, based on the implementation of graphic display tools for chemical data.

Keywords: chemical data ; archaeomaterials ; archaeometallurgy ; archaeometry

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1. Introduction:

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Despite their being consensus for a shared repository for data associated with ironworking (Charlton, 2015), no initiative to establish a global source of reference data had been undertaken until now in the iron archaeometallurgy research field. However, a similar effort has been made by a closely related scientific community interested in amalgamating lead isotope data from non-ferrous metalworking (copper alloys or lead/silver metallurgy), along with metadata (i.e. geolocations, dating, chemical data); known as TerraLID, the initiative was set up in 2009 and now exists on a web portal for common use (Klein et al., 2022). Such initiatives, when they come to fruition, can prove extremely beneficial for a community of researchers. The 'Chimie en PaléoSidérurgie' (CHIPS) database is intended to play such a role for archaeometallurgists of iron. Several members of the Institut de Recherche sur les Archéomatériaux (IRAMAT-CNRS) set about designing a database (DB) management system enabling researchers to easily select geolocated reference data. An interface is being developed in order to facilitate data queries either on categorical (chronology, typology, etc) or spatial data (<https://tinyurl.com/CHIPSdatabase>). This interface is currently only available in French, but an English version is under development. Particular effort has been devoted to documenting analytical metadata (analytical conditions, analysis laboratories), which is essential for assessing data quality. Ultimately, these two databases conceived on similar ontologies could constitute an essential digital reference environment for research in archaeometallurgy. Furthermore, the conceptors of CHIPS are currently working hand-in-hand with colleagues who are developing a database focused on the structuration of contextual information for describing metallurgical contexts (advanced normative description of archaeological material, precise description of smelting technologies, etc.). Both databases will be implemented as a broader information system allowing enhanced description of both contextual and chemical data.

The aim of this article is to present in detail the choices made to design the CHIPS database data model, collate heterogeneous datasets and provide queryable attribute descriptors. Some of the functions of information system are still under development, but the DB can already be used to make basic queries. It is being populated mainly from data that has already been published. A community of users is in the process of building up around this tool, which could rapidly become an essential reference for future research into iron archaeometallurgy.

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2. Background :

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The study of the *chaînes opératoires* and the circulation of materials (mainly ore and metal products) is one of the main thrusts of research into iron archaeometallurgy. These research topics rely heavily on the analysis of chemical data. The chemical composition of products and waste associated with iron- and steelmaking activities enables us, to some extent, to reconstruct the physico-chemical conditions in which metallurgical operations took place (ore preparation, direct smelting, primary and secondary smithing) and therefore to better understand the ways of the ancient metallurgists (Blakelock et al., 2009; Charlton et al., 2010; Dillmann and L'Héritier, 2007; Serneels, 1993; Serneels and Crew, 1997). These studies are necessary to understand the history of techniques, from both materials (physico-chemical processes) and socio-economic perspectives. In addition, several recent studies have shown that it is possible to establish a chemical link between the extracted ore, the workshop that reduced it and the metal products produced by this workshop. These studies have evaluated the potential of numerous chemical markers (Charlton et al., 2012; Dillmann et al., 2017; Disser et al., 2016; Milot et al., 2016; Pagès et al., 2022; Stepanov et al., 2020; Żabiński et al., 2020). These approaches make it possible to partially reconstruct socio-economic systems that have now disappeared, by analysing the circulation of materials (routes taken, distances, etc.).

88 For some forty years, researchers interested in ancient metallurgy have been accumulating
89 chemical data to support their research. However, this documentation is widely dispersed due to
90 the variety of media used to publish the results: printed sheets, tables in PDF or MS Word
91 publications, spreadsheets, and now also raw data files with scripts (for reproducing analyses with
92 statistical software). In addition, the analytical devices used to acquire these data use different
93 physical phenomena (e.g. X-ray fluorescence spectroscopy, mass spectrometry, neutron
94 activation) and have their own characteristics and performance (detection limits, measurement
95 errors, and signal resolution).

96 Finally, archaeometallurgists have various disciplinary backgrounds: geochemistry, materials
97 science and archaeology, which influences the way they represent data. The choices vary
98 according to the authors: stoichiometric representations, quantification in elemental or oxide form,
99 etc. This heterogeneity makes it difficult to collate data for collective use. Collecting, sifting through
100 and merging various datasets to build reference data is a very time-consuming task for individual
101 researchers. A single given project is unlikely to exploit the full potential of the data it generates
102 (sometimes only appreciated with hindsight and in comparison with new datasets), and so the
103 whole point of the semantic web, linked open data (LOD) and the FAIR (Findable, Accessible,
104 Interoperable, Reusable) guidelines is to help align data with standards (i.e. standardisation) to
105 create possibilities for gaining new insights and new opportunities/methods for analysing data.

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3. Design of the CHIPS database

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109 The design of the CHIPS database followed an initial attempt to create a repository in tabular
110 form, but the need to structure the information in the form of a relational DB soon became obvious
111 to ensure data integrity, consistency, longevity and interoperability. It was therefore decided to
112 develop a PostgreSQL DB. Among open-source database management system software,
113 PostgreSQL is the closest to Oracle, the most popular system in the sector of information systems.
114 In addition to the use of SQL, this choice was mainly motivated by the possibility of using its spatial
115 extension PostGIS, which offers the functionalities required for the management of spatialised
116 data, in particular the use of spatialised indexes and geoprocessing. The data is structured around
117 four main tables, which respectively document the archaeological context of discovery
118 ('contexts'), the archaeological material ('samples'), the analysis carried out ('analyses') and
119 the associated measurement errors ('measurement errors'). These four tables will successively
120 be described, along with the parent tables that document each of them. The simplified common
121 data model (CDM) is shown in Figure 1.

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Figure 1 : Simplified MCD of the CHIPS DB

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3.1. 'Contexts' table

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It is composed of 14 fields (primary key: 'context_id') (Table 1). Its purpose is to identify and locate the archaeological contexts, link them to geoadministrative data, and to define their chronology. A context is defined either as a locus, a phase of occupation/activity or a stratigraphic unit. Multiple contexts may be related to the same archaeological site. For example, heaps of slag that have been successively piled up but that are stratigraphically distinct are common on metallurgical sites. Each of these heaps is then considered as a single context, named in the 'context_name' field. The archaeological site of which these heaps are part is registered for each single context in the 'place_name' field. An additional field 'context_type_id' used as a foreign key allows a more precise description of the context: locus, phase, stratigraphical unit, etc. A 'context_type' field with a value constraint is used to express the type of context. The 'locality_id' field acts as a foreign key to the 'gadm' parent table. The Global Administrative Areas (GADM) dataset, published online by UC Davis, contains around 400,000 administrative entities worldwide, documented at five hierarchical levels, from country to municipality (*Global administrative areas boundaries*, 2022). Four fields provide spatial information. The 'srid' field is documented by the 'spatial_ref_sys' table associated with the PostGIS extension, and is used to interpret the coordinates in the 'long' and 'lat' fields (decimal degrees or projected coordinates). In the source documents, the geographic coordinates are expressed in a variety of projection systems, depending on the location of the study area or national administrative recommendations. For France, for example, coordinates are frequently published in the Lambert-93 system (EPSG:2154) (International Organization for Standardization, 2019). The Boolean 'centroid' field indicates whether the coordinates are those of the site, or those of the administrative entity's centroid. Three fields are associated with chronology. The field 'edtf' gathers EDTF (ISO 8601-2:2019) temporal information on the different contexts allowing, among others, to record chronology uncertainties ('?' mark) and approximations ('~' mark).. Along with the 'edtf' field, the 'periodo_id' field links the chronological data to the Periodo gazetteer to ease the definition of the periods of activity. The last field, 'points', is made up of objects of type GEOGRAPHY, produced using the PostGIS ST_MakePoint geospatial function. A field 'cont_bibreference' is used as a foreign key to the 'literature' table. It allows to get access to the documentation related to archaeological data and excavation, as this kind of information is often summarized in the publications dealing with chemical data.

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context_id	context_name	place_name	srid	longitude	latitude	centroid
integer primary key	text	text	integer foreign key	numeric	numeric	boolean
62	Boeng Kroam location 1 (BK1)	Boeng Kroam	4326	105.168	11.0619	true
63	Boeng Kroam location 1 (BK2)	Boeng Kroam	4326	105.168	11.0619	true
399	Chanoi 1	Chanoi	4326	4.78407	47.75319	true
400	Chanoi 2	Chanoi	4326	4.78407	47.75319	true
364	Chemin des Combes	Chemin des Combes	4326	6.36186	47.35265	true
397	L'Abîme US 102	L'Abîme	4326	3.2669	47.4717	false
398	L'Abîme US 104	L'Abîme	4326	3.2669	47.4717	false
76	Chêne Saint- Amand HMA	Chêne Saint- Amand	4326	4.9721	48.625	false
77	Chêne Saint- Amand MA	Chêne Saint- Amand	4326	4.9678	48.6267	false
1593	Chestnut Park	Chestnut Park	4326	-2.3711	51.6261	false
1490	Combe Tabeillon	Combe Tabeillon	4326	7.1563	47.3115	false
1492	Combe Tabeillon 1	Combe Tabeillon	4326	7.1374	47.302	false
1493	Combe Tabeillon 2	Combe Tabeillon	4326	7.1381	47.3019	false

context_type	edtf	points	key_periodo	key_periodo2	locality_id
text	text	geometry	text	text	integer foreign key
locus	1400~/1500~	0101000020E610 0000986E1283C0 4A5A40AB3E575	http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p02chr49ctv		238603
locus	1450~/1750~	0101000020E610 0000986E1283C0 4A5A40AB3E575	http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p02chr49ctv	http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p02chr478fd	238603
locus	-0025~/0450~	0101000020E610 00005019FF3EE3 2213404DD6A88	http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p02chr4964n		71481
locus	1316~/1648~	0101000020E610 00005019FF3EE3 2213404DD6A88	http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p02chr49ctv	http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p02chr478fd	71481
locus	0542/0684	0101000020E610 000018EC866D8 B7219409A779C	http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p02chr49bbg		75236
stratigraphic unit	1295/1401	0101000020E610 0000516B9A779 C220A40F8C264	http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p02chr49ctv		73943
stratigraphic unit	0066/0222	0101000020E610 0000516B9A779 C220A40F8C264	http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p02chr4847s		73943
sequence	0700~/0900~	0101000020E610 000033C4B12E6 EE313400000000	http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p02chr4scv9		62995
sequence	1000~/1200~	0101000020E610 0000744694F606 DF13409C33A2B	http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p02chr458g8		62995
locus	0015?~/0200?~	0101000020E610 0000645DDC460 3F802C04703780	http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p0kh9ds8p8k	http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p0kh9ds9nsj	43238
locus	1000?~/1300?~	0101000020E610 00008E75711B0 DA01C401D5A6	http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p02chr458g8		339128
locus		0101000020E610 0000B1E1E995B 28C1C402DB29D			339128
locus	0900?~/1200?~	0101000020E610 0000764F1E166 A8D1C40CA54C	http://n2t.net/ark:/99152/p02chr4zc8c		339128

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Table 1 : View created from the 'contexts' table, showing 13 examples of contexts

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161 3.2. 'Samples' table

162 It is composed of 5 fields (Table 2). Two fields identify the sample: 'sample_id' is the table's
 163 primary key and 'sample_name' field is the identifier given by the archaeologist during the post-
 164 excavation study of the material, or a code given when the sample was taken. 'site_id' is the
 165 foreign key referencing the context in which the artefacts were found. A 'comment' field allows a
 166 more precise yet less standardised description of the sample if needed. The 'id_typo' field is filled
 167 in by the 'typology' table, the aim of which is to obtain as precise information as possible on the
 168 artefacts, while ensuring the effectiveness of categorical queries.

169 The 'typology' table therefore has a hierarchical structure with five levels (Table 3). The first
 170 level 'process' corresponds to the ironmaking process in question, i.e. the direct or indirect
 171 process. Establishing this difference is fundamental, since the *chaînes opératoires* and physico-
 172 chemical processes involved are radically different. The data associated with either process cannot
 173 therefore be compared directly. The 'context' field specifies whether the material was collected

174 in a geological (i.e. extra-site, for ore or earth), archaeological (i.e. intra-site) or experimental
 175 context. The 'material' field indicates the nature of the artefact: slag, earth, ore, rock, etc. The
 176 'category' field is the first level of qualification for the material. For the material slag, this qualifier
 177 could be ore smelting or metal forging, for example. The 'subcategory' field is the second level of
 178 qualification, which can give even more details about the material. For a smelting slag, this second
 179 level can be used to determine whether the slag is moulded at the bottom of the furnace, or whether
 180 it has flowed out of the furnace. This level of precision is necessary to accurately interpret the
 181 archaeological context and the associated chemical data. A last field 'ark_frantic' references
 182 each typological entity with an ARK permanent identifier linked to the Pactols thesaurus. This
 183 aspect will be further developed in section 4.1.

sample_id	sample_name	context_id	typology_id	comments
integer primary key	text	integer foreign key	integer foreign key	text
6797	VG_1b	1744	24	Microlammellar hematite
6805	TN-2	1746	24	Lamellar/micaceous hematite with pyrite
6813	6997	1748	24	Massive goethite with calcite
6795	VIG_M	1742	24	Lamellar/micaceous hematite
6819	4526/b	1751	24	Hematite-bearing schist
6809	TN-9	1746	24	Micaceous hematite
6836	11007	1764	24	Micaceous hematite
6824	901	1756	24	hematite with calcite
6812	2914	1748	24	Brown–reddish massive goethite
6838	16259	1765	24	Fibrous-radiated hematite
6814	7231	1749	24	Micaceous hematite (Montomoli shaft)

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Table 2 : View created from the 'samples' table, showing 11 sample examples

typology_id	process	context	material	category	subcategory	ark_frantic_uri
integer primary key	text	text	text	text	text	text
161	Indirect	Experimental	Metal	Cast iron	NULL	https://ark.frantiq.fr/ark:/26678/pcrtTc_vLDTNT86
190	Direct	Archaeological	Earth	Molten	NULL	https://ark.frantiq.fr/ark:/26678/pcrt5b_IL1UtwcT
15	Direct	Archaeological	Slag	Smithing	Hearth bottom	https://ark.frantiq.fr/ark:/26678/pcrtfvI_QbnsSeS
16	Direct	Experimental	Slag	Smithing	Hearth bottom	https://ark.frantiq.fr/ark:/26678/pcrtfvI_QbnsSeS
3	Direct	Archaeological	Slag	Smelting	NULL	https://ark.frantiq.fr/ark:/26678/pcrtzh_OWtynBny
24	Unknown	Geological	Ore	Smelting	NULL	https://ark.frantiq.fr/ark:/26678/pcrt5b
5	Direct	Archaeological	Slag	Smelting	Tap slag	https://ark.frantiq.fr/ark:/26678/pcrtzh_OWtynBny
10	Direct	Experimental	Slag	Smelting	Slag block	https://ark.frantiq.fr/ark:/26678/pcrtzh_OWtynBny
63	Direct	Archaeological	Earth	Baked clay	Lining	https://ark.frantiq.fr/ark:/26678/pcrtfx_4s0yvSLj
69	Indirect	Archaeological	Slag	Smelting	Blast furnace slag	https://ark.frantiq.fr/ark:/26678/pcrtzh_OWtynBny
62	Direct	Experimental	Earth	Baked clay	Tuyere	https://ark.frantiq.fr/ark:/26678/pcrtwJ_getoWYz9

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Table 3 : View created from the 'typology' table, showing 11 examples of types

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189 3.3. 'Analyses' table

190 This table contains 97 fields. The 'sample_id' field is the foreign key to the 'samples' table.
191 Multiple analyses can be related to a single sample. Each of these analyses is implemented as
192 distinct rows in the 'analyses' table and therefore have a single 'chips_id'. Three other fields are
193 foreign keys to a table listing the analytical devices used to perform the analyses. We distinguish
194 between 'major_setup_id', 'trace_setup_id' and 'isotope_setup_id', corresponding
195 respectively to the equipment used to measure major elements, trace elements and isotopes
196 (Table 4). These three categories of chemical data are often acquired by distinct instruments. Most
197 analytical methods are documented either through scientific papers or through technical

198 documents which make it possible to determine reference values for detection limits and
 199 measurement uncertainties. This aspect will be detailed in section 0. A 'bibreference' field is
 200 documented by a 'literature' table, which gives the database user access to the publications
 201 associated with the analyses (Table 5). At present, the table includes 69 fields expressing chemical
 202 data, which form the core of the database. Of these, 65 are absolute concentrations of chemical
 203 elements. Fourteen fields relating to the contents of O, Na, Mg, Al, Si, P, S, Cl, K, Ca, Ti, Mn and
 204 Fe, as well as the loss on ignition, are expressed by weight percent (wt%). The 'os_ppt' field is
 205 filled in with contents expressed in ng.kg⁻¹. The fifty other fields associated with contents are
 206 expressed in mg.kg⁻¹ (International Organization for Standardization, 2007). Four other fields
 207 document isotopic ratios. Depending on the type of analysis carried out, only some of the chemical
 208 elements are measured. Thus, for a given analysis, the absence of measurement is expressed by
 209 the constant NULL. The concentration of a given element may be too low to be reliably quantified.
 210 It is therefore considered as below the detection limit. We have decided to represent this data in
 211 the form of a single numerical value '-1'. Being negative makes this value easy to distinguish from
 212 elemental contents or isotopic ratios, whose values are systematically positive. It is common
 213 practice to replace values below detection limits in data analysis, so as not to exclude the values
 214 of other variables for a given individual. The CHIPS database user therefore has the possibility of
 215 applying a replacement rule for the '-1' values in the exported dataset.

chips_id	sample_id	major_setup_id	trace_setup_id	silicium	iron	arsenic	zirconium
integer primary key	integer foreign key	integer foreign	integer foreign	numeric	numeric	numeric	numeric
152	152	10	11	8.87	41.58	10.3	171.5
655	655	8	9	9.42	29.52	5.76	246
664	664	8	9	11.25	25.14	-1	208.1
665	665	8	9	8.3	32.83	2.09	180.5
672	672	8	9	9.06	28.83	117.7	125.9
725	725	8	9	8.5	42.79	3.32	220
884	884	8	9	7.7	30.13	167	114
1121	1121	4	7	11.71	42.86	11.26	998.75
1269	1269	4	7	8.27	56.37	4.31	15.78
1281	1281	4	7	16.57	37.79	0.39	36.13

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218 Table 4 : View created from the 'analyses' table, showing 11 analyses examples.
 219 Only 4 out of the 69 fields related to chemical contents are displayed.

literature_id	authors	title	media	volume	issue
Integer primary key	text	text	text	integer	integer
6	Philippe Dillmann, Roland Schwab, Sylvain Bauvais, Michael Brauns, Alexandre Disser, Stéphanie Leroy, Guntram Gassmann, Philippe Fluzin	Circulation of iron products in the North-Alpine area during the end of the first Iron Age (6th-5th c. BC): A combination of chemical and isotopic approaches	Journal of Archaeological Science	87	NULL
8	Anne-Marie Desaulty	Apport des analyses chimiques multi technique à la compréhension du comportement des éléments traces dans les filières sidérurgiques anciennes.	NULL	NULL	NULL
9	Jean Milot, Franck Poitrasson, Sandrine Baron, Marie-Pierre Coustures	Iron isotopes as a potential tool for ancient iron metals tracing	Journal of Archaeological Science	76	NULL

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publication_year	pages	url	doi	publication_type
integer	text	text	text	text
2017	108-124	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0305440317301486#fig4	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jas.2017.10.002	Article
2008	NULL	https://theses.hal.science/tel-00552060	NULL	Thesis
2016	NULL	https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0305440316301480#bib61	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jas.2016.10.003	Article

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Table 5 : View created from the 'literature' table, showing 3 reference examples.

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224 3.4. 'errors' table

225 This table consists of 91 fields. An 'error_id' field is the table's primary key (Table 6). The
 226 'chips_id' field is a foreign key referenced in the 'analyses' table. The 89 other fields contain
 227 values which correspond to the uncertainties associated with each measurement in the 'analyses'
 228 database, expressed as mass fractions (either percents, mg.kg⁻¹, or ng.kg⁻¹) (International
 229 Organization for Standardization, 2007). These values are either provided directly by the authors
 230 in the context of certain publications, or calculated according to a protocol which will be detailed in
 231 section 4.2.

error_id	chips_id	silicon_error	iron_error	arsenic_error	zirconium_error
integer primary key	integer foreign key	numeric	numeric	numeric	numeric
152	152	0.1774	4.158	NULL	NULL
655	655	0.942	0.5904	1.152	12.3
664	664	0.225	0.5028	NULL	10.405
665	665	0.83	0.6566	0.418	9.025
672	672	0.906	0.5766	5.885	6.295
725	725	0.85	0.8558	0.664	11
884	884	0.77	0.6026	8.35	5.7
1121	1121	0.2342	0.8572	NULL	NULL
1269	1269	0.1654	1.1274	NULL	NULL
1281	1281	0.3314	0.7558	NULL	NULL

Table 6 : View created from the 'error' table, showing 10 series of measurement error values, associated to the measurements shown in Table 4.

4. Purposes and functionalities

Data interoperability is a central outcome of the DB. Users must be able to extract the data and use it directly, without having to convert it, which would require a very large amount of documentation and a considerable amount of time. We have also focused on assessing the quality of the data, so that users can easily check whether they may encounter any quality-related biases (missing data, measurement error, etc.) when analysing the data.

4.1. Data collation and standards

Chemical data: handling compositional data requires some precautions to be taken to ensure that no bias is introduced by the data format. Several disciplinary communities are interested in chemical data related to iron metallurgy. As a result of their developments, these communities have defined conventions for representing chemical information that are more or less specific to them.

In our case, geochemists will tend to represent the mass fractions of chemical elements in the form of oxides. This form seems more adequate with rocks and minerals in which simple pure bodies are very rare. Silicon is therefore always represented by its most abundant compound form, silica SiO_2 . Nevertheless, it has to be stressed out that representing chemical composition through oxides is an abstraction. For example, iron smelting slag is by far not mainly composed of quartz of tridymite (SiO_2), but of fayalite (Fe_2SiO_4), leucite (KAlSi_2O_6) or kirschsteinite ($\text{CaFe}^{2+}\text{SiO}_4$). In the materials sciences, the representations are more varied, and it is common to see the contents expressed in elementary mass fractions. Silica would then be represented by two contents, silicon and oxygen. In the documentation used to populate the CHIPS database, it is common to see the mass fraction of the same element represented by several oxides. Manganese, for example, is sometimes represented as Mn_3O_4 , sometimes as MnO ; iron as FeO and Fe_2O_3 . Data expressed in two different forms are not directly comparable. 10 wt% Fe_2O_3 corresponds to 6.99 wt% Fe, while 10 wt% FeO corresponds to 7.77 wt% Fe. In order to avoid multiple alternative descriptors for the same chemical element, and to have comparable data sets, it was decided to represent the quantifications calculated as element weight percent. To achieve this, all the data expressed in terms of oxide content were converted by the corresponding stoichiometric factors before being included in the DB.

267 Spatial and administrative data: the administrative data of each archaeological context is
268 documented by a top-down hierarchy of up to five levels, depending on the administrative
269 complexity of the country in question. Queries can therefore be made at national, regional,
270 provincial, etc. level for any data. This documentation is currently provided by version 4.1 of the
271 Global Administrative Areas (GADM) directory. Alignment with the GeoNames gazetteer, which is
272 increasingly becoming the reference standard, is planned. Spatial data is expressed in accordance
273 with the corresponding EPSG, enabling the correct calculation of GEOGRAPHY type objects that
274 are projected via the display interface.

275 Categorical data (typo-functional description of the archaeological material): this is referenced
276 according to two systems. The first system is a hierarchical list of terms drawn up on the basis of
277 joint discussions among a board of archaeometallurgy specialists (Table 3). The entries are
278 currently translated into two languages, French and English. The second system is the Pactols
279 multilingual thesaurus (v2.0). It is based on the DARIAH-EU Backbone Thesaurus, which is
280 compatible with the CIDOC-CRM ontology. This choice was made because this controlled
281 vocabulary makes it possible to homogenise the data in line with the structure we have adopted to
282 describe the materials analysed. This facilitates the integration of the CHIPS database into
283 archaeological data (Katsianis et al., 2023). The description of individuals is less precise than that of
284 the first system, but the terms are translated into six different languages and allow easy alignment
285 with other thesauri such as the Getty Institute's Art & Architecture Thesaurus (AAT).

286

287 **4.2. Data quality and accuracy**

288 The quality or accuracy of three types of information is assessed by means of indicators in the
289 DB. The accuracy of the spatial data is expressed by a Boolean which indicates whether the
290 coordinates of each entity in the 'contexts' table correspond to the actual location of the
291 archaeological context. If the precise coordinates are not documented, the entity is placed on the
292 centroid of the administrative entity concerned, generally the location of the building housing the
293 administrative authority (town hall, county, etc.). Knowing the accuracy of this data can be
294 important for spatial analyses, particularly on a micro-regional scale, for example when analysing
295 ore mining and transport strategies. As already mentioned, chronological data quality is managed
296 using the Extended Date/Time Format (EDTF) ISO standard notation. By convention historical
297 periods interval are expressed with approximations marks on their interval. The quality of the
298 chronological data is also assessed by a Boolean, which indicates whether the authors of the
299 source documents consider the dating of the archaeological context to be fuzzy. When absolute
300 dates are given by the authors, they are put in the database as such. If a period is mentioned, the
301 commonly accepted intervals for the period are entered in the database. For example, sites dated
302 to phase C1 of the Roman era in Poland are expressed as 150~/250~', indicating the interval [150
303 ; 250].

304 Given that chemical information is at the heart of the DB, particular attention was paid to
305 qualifying data quality. This is expressed in the form of measurement errors. Each analytical device
306 has its own characteristics that influence the trueness and precision of the measurements. To
307 determine trueness, standard materials are used whose precise chemical composition is known.
308 The differences between the known value and the measured values express the accuracy
309 (International Organization for Standardization, 2023). Repeatability is determined by carrying out a
310 series of measurements on the same material, and studying the dispersion of the measured values
311 around the mean value of the series. Standard deviation is usually used as indicator. The
312 qualification of these factors have been widely discussed within the archaeological community,
313 e.g. (Hughes, 1998; Nazaroff et al., 2010; Frahm, 2012). In the case of CHIPS, it has been decided
314 to use a single factor to express the quality of the measurement: the measurement error. This error
315 is a function of the factors we have just mentioned. A large number of methods can be used to
316 calculate these values, a good summary of which has been published by (Buonaccorsi, 2010). The
317 value of the measurement error is also influenced by the abundance of the element measured in
318 the material. The closer is the measurement to the instrument's detection limits, the greater the

319 error. Most analytical laboratories use reference values to express measurement errors.
320 Measurement errors are generally expressed in relative terms, as a fraction of the measured value
321 (e.g. 5%). In some cases, these values are given in concentration intervals, to take account of the
322 influence of abundance that has just been mentioned. These values are communicated either
323 through scientific articles (as in our case(Carignan et al., 2001)) or technical documentation. Each
324 time new data is filled in the 'analyses' table, related with analytical setups for which uncertainties
325 Of the 33 analytical devices currently listed, only 46 have sufficiently precise documentation to
326 determine measurement uncertainties. However, these 9 devices represent 2,122 out of the 3,004
327 open analyses in the DB, i.e. around 70%. Further documentation work will be carried out to extend
328 this functionality to other analytical devices. In any case, this functionality is proving very useful to
329 users in highlighting possible data processing biases due to analytical parameters. are known,a
330 function is triggered to automatically calculate the associated measurement errors. The detailed
331 protocol for recording measurement errors and the trigger function are explained in detail in the
332 online DB documentation : <https://irammat.github.io/chips/en/docs/>.
333

334 5. Reusability

335
336 The CHIPS architecture and CRUD (Create, Read, Update, Delete) policies aim to address the
337 challenges emerging with the unfolding of the third revolution in Archaeology—driven, among other
338 factors, by new IT infrastructures and the online availability of very large databases and datasets—
339 which began more than ten years ago (Kristiansen, 2014). Archaeological data are now massive,
340 multi-paradigmatic, and collectively constructed. Managing them through robust data management
341 plans (data lifecycles) and developing linked open data strategies underpinned by FAIR principles
342 has become even more critical in the era of open science and the rise of machine learning.

343 To meet these new challenges in archaeometallurgy and ensure data interoperability, we set
344 up a copy of the CHIPS instance hosted on the *Fabrique Numérique du Passé* platform—providing
345 strong IT security but restricted database administrator permissions (limited to the authors)—within
346 a more permissive environment that allows further IT application integration. We deployed a
347 development version of CHIPS on an Ubuntu virtual machine hosted on the *Cloud@VirtualData*
348 platform of the Mésocentre Paris-Saclay (<https://virtualdata.fr/>, see below). Regular data-only
349 dumps from CHIPS to CHIPS-dev are carried out using a bash script.

350

351 5.1. The GEO app and the the 'Fabrique Numérique du Passé' platform hosting

352 The DB is currently hosted on a shared web hosting solution granted by the Huma-Num
353 research infrastructure (IR* Huma-Num), DARIAH-EU's national body (France), through a
354 PostgreSQL 15 server running in SSL mode. This solution was chosen because it provides long-
355 term hosting of the database, within an infrastructure whose hardware and technologies are kept
356 up to date. The database has been integrated into the 'Fabrique Numérique du Passé' platform,
357 dedicated to the open sharing of scientific research data and compliant with the FAIR principles
358 (Costa, 2023). A data query interface was set up by the Huma-Num 'Projets Time Machine'
359 consortium, using the GEO software developed by Business Geografic. A cartographic solution
360 has been privileged, as the most appropriate to meet the needs of the users. It is useful to compare
361 the spatial distribution of CHIPS data with other sources of information, such as geological maps.
362 This makes it possible to consider the exploitation of nearby mineral resources, to facilitate data
363 searches in the geochemical documentation, or even to plan field interventions (sampling, for
364 example).

365 Each context is represented by a circular marker whose size depends on the number of
366 analyses available. Cartographic representation can also be used to select entities according to
367 spatial criteria, such as proximity. Spatial queries can be performed using predefined geometric

368 shapes (ellipses, quadrilaterals) or free-form polygons. Queries based on administrative criteria
 369 have also been implemented. These can be performed on two hierarchical levels: country, and
 370 province/region/state. A search by sample name has also been implemented. At present, this
 371 search can only select a sample by its full name, but it is planned to include the Postgres
 372 extensions `pg_trgm` and `fuzzystrmatch`, which enable fuzzy matching on character strings, and
 373 to set up a LIKE query based on a search for values containing a given character string. Finally, a
 374 query based on chronological criteria is available. This works by defining a date interval, using two
 375 boxes, start date and end date. The query returns contexts whose start date is greater than or
 376 equal to the input value, and whose end date is less than or equal to the input value for end date.
 377 Queries based on the nature of the material being analysed are also planned. This will enable, for
 378 example, the selection of ore analyses only. Once the contexts selected, the data can be consulted
 379 using several nested forms. These show successively geo-administrative data for the context, data
 380 concerning the samples analyzed (sample name, typology), and chemical data divided into three
 381 subwindows (major elements, trace elements, isotopes) (Figure 2). A final sub-section lists the
 382 bibliographic references from which the analyses come.

383
 384 Figure 2 : Example of chemical data visualization for a sample coming from the
 385 'Noires Terres' archaeological context (blue marker highlighted on the cartographic
 386 view)
 387

388 5.2. The CHIPS RESTful API

389 Alongside the ready-to-use GEO app, we deployed a standalone PostgREST web server to
 390 expose a selection of CHIPS views as RESTful API endpoints. To demonstrate the value of
 391 archaeometallurgical chemical data reusability, we chose to first publish views of previously
 392 normalised datasets together with their bibliographic references. While PostgREST provides online
 393 access to raw data, we also deployed a Python dashboard that consumes these data in order to
 394 model the different datasets and provide a synoptic view of the CHIPS database content (Figure
 395 3).
 396

Welcome

This dashboard helps Exploring The CHIPS Database. See also

Datasets

- [dataset_tyoungxx](#)
- [dataset_adisser17](#)
- [dataset_gzabinski23](#)
- [dataset_gpages22](#)
- [dataset_vserneels93](#)
- [dataset_sleroy12](#)
- [dataset_pdlilmann17](#)
- [dataset_amdesaulty8a](#)
- [dataset_amdesaulty8b](#)
- [dataset_jmilot16](#)
- [dataset_mpcoustures06](#)
- [dataset_gstddier17](#)
- [dataset_mbrauns13](#)
- [dataset_lheritier20](#)
- [dataset_mleroy97](#)
- [dataset_mleroy24](#)
- [dataset_leschenlohr01](#)
- [dataset_tivancan21](#)
- [dataset_pmameli14](#)
- [dataset_kmittelstaedt22](#)

397

398

399 Figure 3: Two views of the CHIPS dashboard (<https://iram-at-apps.cnrs.fr/dash/>).
400 Top: Landing page of the CHIPS dashboard, showing the spatial distribution of
401 CHIPS interoperable (API-based) datasets. Bottom: A selection from the dataset by
402 Grzegorz Żabiński et al. (2023), displayed as a Plotly line chart in log₁₀ scale
403 (https://iram-at-apps.cnrs.fr/dash/dataset_gzabinski23). This dashboard page also
404 provides access to the raw data from Grzegorz Żabiński et al. (2023) in JSON format
405 (http://157.136.252.188:3000/dataset_gzabinski23), and allows filtering by site and
406 sample.

407
408 While the CHIPS dashboard aims to provide a synoptic view of the database content for dataset
409 selection, we have started to develop an R package (<https://github.com/iram-at/iRamat>) for more
410 refined and advanced statistical analysis. Currently, this package includes only a limited number
411 of functions (one of which connects to and retrieves data from the API) and serves primarily as a
412 prototype (Figure 4). With the iRamat package, our goal is to foster collaboration among
413 archaeometallurgists—potentially alongside their datasets—in order to build a collective tool useful
414 to the community, helping to standardise and make archaeometallurgical data more reusable.

```
df <- db_api_connect()
plots <- chrono(df$dataset_adisser17, use_periodo = TRUE)
ggpubr::ggarrange(plots$sites, plots$periodo$periodo,
  heights = c(1, 2), ncol = 1, align = "v")
```


415
 416 Figure 4: Screenshot of the README.md page of the iRamat R package
 417 (<https://github.com/iramatiRamat>), showing the output of the chrono() function. At
 418 the top, eighteen site time spans (in EDTF) are displayed from the Disser et al.
 419 (2017) CHIPS dataset, retrieved via the dataset's raw data API
 420 (http://157.136.252.188:3000/dataset_adisser17). At the bottom, the PeriodO
 421 periods are shown from the authority "INRAP: Institut National de Recherches
 422 Archéologiques Préventives. PACTOLS chronology periods used in DOLIA data.
 423 2021" (n2t.net/ark:/99152/p02chr4).

424

425

6. Perspectives

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435

Core developments. The CHIPS DB is now at an advanced stage of development. The conceptual model has been tried and tested, and allows the smooth running of functions already set up. The next stages of development will focus on improving the data query interface, in particular by proposing new queries. The database currently provides open access to 3004 chemical analyses relating to 581 archaeological context. Nevertheless, the database contains a total of 7314 analyses from 1298 different contexts. Moderation work is underway to ensure that the dissemination of these analyses complies with legislation on the protection of intellectual property rights. The repository will also soon be enriched by the integration of structural data, such as the results of X-ray diffraction analyses. Data will be expressed in fractions of mineralogical

436 species (e.g. hematite, siderite, quartz, etc.). These data will be particularly useful for describing
437 ore samples, and enabling further interpretation of the geological contexts in which they were
438 extracted.

439 **User community.** We are looking to structure a community of users around the DB in a bottom-
440 up organization with the aim of a collaborative research. The use of this tool will provide an
441 opportunity to think collectively about the production of archaeometallurgical chemical data from
442 different perspectives: intercomparability, reference materials, analytical protocols. The rules for
443 contributions, the contributions themselves, the intellectual property of the data, as well as their
444 reuse rules (<https://iramam.github.io/chips/data/how-to-cite/>) are made explicit in a transparent way
445 on the documentation website of the DB. We envisage a CC-BY license for the data, CC0 for the
446 metadata, ODbL for the DB and MIT for the computer code.

447 **Expanding the DB.** An international communication campaign is being conducted via a
448 webinar and a mailing list. . A workflow for feeding the DB with further datasets is proposed on the
449 website (<https://iramam.github.io/chips/data/how-to-contribute/>). This will lead to the import of
450 several new datasets in the near future, conducted by members from the user community. The
451 data will be moderated prior to their integration in the DB.

452 The initial communication campaigns around the CHIPS database have also aroused interest
453 among researchers who are not strictly speaking interested in iron archaeometallurgy. For
454 example, ore is a cultural term (to identify a rock/mineral from which metal can be extracted; the
455 same rock/mineral may instead be used as a pigment material or colourant in another technological
456 practice, and so its function/identification is contingent on its use and the context. More generally,
457 the conceptual data model of the CHIPS database can be used to create chemical reference
458 systems for the study of other archaeological materials, such as glass or copper alloys.
459

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462

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475

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